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ANALYZING THE PERFORMANCE OF ANDHRA PRADESH STATE FINANCIAL CORPORATION: AN APPROACH BASED ON THE CAMEL'S FRAMEWORK
• DR. P. SANGEETHA

ABSTRACT:

Indian banking system has transformed in recent years due to globalization in the world market, which has resulted in fierce competition. In this article, an attempt has been made to analyze the performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation. For the purpose of ranking CAMEL, analysis technique has been used. Each parameter of CAMEL—Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Management Efficiency, Earning Quality and Liquidity has been evaluated taking these five ratios, and a final composite index has been developed. The results shown capital adequacy, assets quality, management efficiency and liquidity positions are good but earning quality is to be improved.

Key words: Performance, CAMEL's framework, Capital Adequacy, Earning Quality, Management Efficiency.

INTRODUCTION:

The idea of establishing specialized institutions for the provision of finance for industry was given by different commissions and committees long before independence and finally took concrete shape with the establishment of APSPFC, Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation is a lending institution established in 1956 for promoting small and medium scale industries in Andhra Pradesh under the provisions of the State Financial Corporations Act, 1951. The Corporation came into existence on 1-11-1956 by merger of Andhra State Financial Corporation and Hyderabad State Financial Corporation. The corporation has launched many entrepreneur-friendly schemes to provide term loans, working capital term loans and special and seed capital assistance to suit the needs of various categories of entrepreneurs. The Corporation has completed five decades of dedicated service in industrial financing of tiny, small and medium scale sector units and contributing to the balanced regional development of the state.

In this way, one of the most popular methods for the analysis and evaluation of the APSPFC soundness is represented by the CAMEL's framework. The aim of our research is to analyze the financial soundness of the APSPFC that operate in Andhra Pradesh.

CAMEL RATING MODEL:

In 1995, RBI had set up a working group under the chairmanship of Shri. S. Padmanabhan to review the banking supervision system. The committee made certain recommendations and suggestions on this model, a rating system for domestic and foreign banks based on the international CAMEL's model combining financial management and systems & control elements were introduced for the inspection cycle commencing from July 1998. It recommended that the banks should be rated on a five point scale (1to5) based on the lines of international CAMEL's rating model. The operational efficiency of the cooperative credit institutions is examined through the CAMEL (Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Management efficiency, Earnings quality, and Liquidity) model. That evaluates five key ingredient of operating performance. The efficiency parameters in the model are well defined and embedded in a composite frame to rate the operating performance as described below:

The numerics in the braces are CAMEL ratings. The number (1) indicates the highest rating strongest performance, least degree of supervision concern, and sound health, while (5)

Indicates lowest rating, inadequate performance and weak health of bank and, therefore, receiving the highest degree of supervisory concern. The efficiency Parameters identified in the (CAMEL) model is defined as below:

- Capital Adequacy (Risk weighted capital to assets): It reflects the financial condition of the bank and specifies the quality and level of capital required to meet additional requirements of funds for a bank. Rating (1) indicates strong capital level which adequately supports the risk profile while rating (5) indicates inadequate capital signifying an urgent need for external capital to sustain the operations.
 - Assets Quality (NPA to Sanctions): one of the indicators for asset quality is the ratio of non-performing loans to Sanctions. It is judged in terms of potential credit risk associated with the lending. It acts as testing instrument to reflect the ability of management in discovering and controlling risk. Higher NPA is an indicative of poor credit decision making. Rating (1) indicates strong asset quality and very good credit monitoring and administration while rating (5) indicates critically deficient asset quality severely affecting bank viability.
 - Management Efficiency (Net profit to employees): It is a measured evaluation of management and is subjective in nature. But, the paper tries to give a partner that reflects the quality of management based on the information available in the balance sheet of the bank. The paper uses net profit to employee ratio to suggest on the efficiency of the man power in the bank. Rating (1) indicates higher efficiency of the employees of the bank, while rating (5) indicates a critically deficient management efficiency of the employees. The bank is not earning enough. This may be due to the failure of the bank to utilize its employee force effectively.
 - Earnings quality (Net Profit after tax to average assets): The earnings of a bank reflect its growth capacity and financial health. In the present study, earnings quality of a bank is measured as return on assets. It measures the efficiency in utilization of assets by the banks. A higher value of ROA denotes higher profitability and high CAMEL rating for the bank. The satisfactory level (1) indicates that the bank has a strong earning quality. The rating (2) indicates satisfactory level (3) indicates less than satisfactory. (4) indicates poor level and (5) indicates critically deficient level of earnings quality.
 - Liquidity Management (Cash to Recoveries): Liquidity for a bank implies the cash position of a bank. In other words, the ability of the bank to meet its customer's day to day cash needs. However sometimes due to various reasons may suddenly face huge amount of withdraws. In such times, a bank is answerable to its customers. In this study, the liquidity of a bank is measured by using cash to deposit ratio. The rating (1) indicates strong liquidity level of the bank. Rating (2) indicates satisfactory liquidity. (3) indicates less than satisfactory. (4) indicates poor level and rating (5) indicates critically deficient liquidity position of the bank.
- The scope of the study covers a period of ten years and the requisite data was compiled from the annual accounts of the APSPFC from the financial year 2000-01 to 2012-13. The NABARD, an apex financial institution has been regulating the affairs of the cooperative credit institutions by providing guidelines and emphasizing on development Action Plan (DAP) to be implemented by the weak cooperative institutions for financial strengthening, operational efficiency, sustained viability, improved profitability and to ensure remedial action in the weak areas. DAP was intended to emphasize on tackling the problems of the cooperative credit institutions in a holistic manner to improve financial performance and the credit viability in a systematic and scientific manner. In spite of these dedicated efforts, the management efficiency, earning quality and the liquidity position of these banks has deteriorated over the years during the course of the study as evident from the information reported in the table 1 and table 2. In

order to examine the financial and operational efficiency, the CAMEL model is applied and the results interpreted through this model are showing vulnerable condition of the district central cooperative banks in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The first studies undertaken on the subject of banks and financial corporation's performance have appeared in the late 1980s and the early 1990s, employing one of the two model types: the Market Power (MP) model or the Efficiency Structure (ES) model (Mensur Zouari, 2010). With the development of the analysis methods, the studies on banks profitability and soundness have evolved from the previous mentioned both on the banks performance and its models based on empirical evidence that were focused both on the bank size plays a significant role in the determinants. Most of these studies underline that the bank size however being still a subject of intense debate. There is large body of academic literature that underlines a positive link between the size of a banking institution and its determinants (e.g. Molynoux and Selby, 1998; Pill off and Rhoades, 2002; Sufian, 2009).

In recent years one of the most used models for the estimation of a bank performances and soundness is represented by the CAMEL'S framework (Borral, 2005). This system is used also as a bank supervision instrument by the regulatory authorities (Gilbert et al, 2000; Hays et al, 2009).

Derviz et Podplera, 2008 One of the most comprehensive studies on banks soundness in the new European Union member states that employs CAMEL'S is represented by the research of Derviz et Podplera (2008) on the Czech Republic banking sector. The study underlines the evolution of the financial soundness for the five largest Czech banks in the pre and post privatization period, namely 1999 to 2005.

CAMEL framework is to analyze the performances of the Northern Cyprus banking sector. The research is focused on the five largest banks in the post 2001 period. The results suggest that the profitability and the management quality of the analysed banks have improved during the analysed period of time, while deterioration has been registered in the capital adequacy and liquidity level.

Abuiescu et Coroiu (2009) and Dardac et Molinescu (2009). Thus, our research intends to fill this gap by providing an analysis of the financial soundness for the Romanian banking sector in the pre and post crisis period.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY:

COLLECTION OF DATA AND ITS ANALYSIS METHOD:

The present study is based on the secondary Data extracted from the annual reports of APSC from 2000-01 to 2012-13, from which financial structure of the corporation has been taken. The collected data were analyzed by using statistical tools and techniques namely Correlation and Regression Analysis. In order to get the results, statistical software such as MS-Excel and SPSS has been used. Charts and Figures had been prepared for presenting and simplifying the process of analysis.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

Main objectives of the study are as follows

- ❖ To study and analyze the financial and operational performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- ❖ To know the Capital Structure Performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- ❖ To identify Impact of profitability on Capital Structure of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
- Hypotheses For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:
 - ❖ Capital Adequacy is not an indicator of capital structure of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
 - ❖ Assets Quality is not an indicator of operational performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
 - ❖ Management Efficiency is not an indicator of financial performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
 - ❖ Earning Quality is not an indicator of profitability performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.
 - ❖ Liquidity is not an indicator of operational performance of Andhra Pradesh State Financial Corporation.

Table 1 CAMEL Model- Efficiency Parameters

Source: Predictions

S.No.	Efficiency parameters	Measurement Ratios	Rating (five point scale)
1	Capital Adequacy	Capital Adequacy	Less than 15(1) 5(4) 15(3) 11-15(2) More than 15(1)
2	Assets Quality	NPA to Advance	More than 50(3) 40-50(4) 30-40(2) 20-30(1)
3	Management	Net profit for employees	Less than 15(1) 15-20(2) 20-25(3) 25-30(4) 30-35(5)
4	Earning Quality	Return on Assets	Less than 15(1) 15-20(2) 20-25(3) 25-30(4) 30-35(5)
5	Liquidity Position	Cash to Recoveries	Less than 5(1) 5-10(2) 10-15(3) 15-20(4) 20-25(5)

Table 2 Financial Parameter Ratings and CAMEL Model Specifications for APSC, 2001-2013

YEAR	Capital Adequacy	Assets Quality	Management Efficiency	Earning Quality	Liquidity Position
2000 - 01	3.25(4)	48.0(4)	-1.6(5)	-9.2(1)	19(2)
2001 - 02	3.84(4)	54.4(5)	-2.2(5)	-7.0(1)	10(4)
2002 - 03	3.65(4)	55.8(5)	4.32(4)	1.8(4)	18(3)
2003 - 04	4.60(4)	61.3(5)	1.9(4)	8.4(2)	1.6(5)

YEAR	Weighted Average Capital (Rs.Millions)	Assets (Rs.Millions)	CAR
2000 - 01	4100	1257.88	3.25
2001 - 02	4562	1188.15	3.84
2002 - 03	4575	1253.28	3.65
2003 - 04	5523	1200.73	4.60
2004 - 05	3507	1192.82	2.94
2005 - 06	5497	1284.46	4.28
2006 - 07	8659	1419.44	6.10
2007 - 08	29535	1840.18	16.05
2008 - 09	19342	1387.53	13.94
2009 - 10	2600	1365.15	15.09
2010 - 11	19698	1212.95	16.24
2011 - 12	40915	2617.73	15.63
2012 - 13	43326	2985.95	14.51

Table 3, Capital adequacy Ratio (Risk weighted Capital to Assets) in brackets are CAMEL Ratings, 1=Best, 5 Worst

YEAR	Weighted Average Capital (Rs.Millions)	Assets (Rs.Millions)	CAR
2000 - 01	4100	1257.88	3.25
2001 - 02	4562	1188.15	3.84
2002 - 03	4575	1253.28	3.65
2003 - 04	5523	1200.73	4.60
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2006 - 07	8659	1419.44	6.10
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2010 - 11	19698	1212.95	16.24
2011 - 12	40915	2617.73	15.63
2012 - 13	43326	2985.95	14.51

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2000-01 to 2012-13.

Figure 1, Capital Adequacy Ratio

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2000-01 to 2012-13.

INFERENCE: The results in Table 3 and figure 1 have shown that the level of capital in APSFC has been satisfactory. SFC has been rated first rank up to 2005-06, thereafter has rated second rank. It signifies that there are sufficient funds to meet its risk profile. It generates more funds and utilized purposefully. It can be seen that the CAR is fluctuate and satisfactory from 2007 to 2013.

Table 4, Assets Quality Ratio

YEAR	NPA (Rs.Millions)	Sanctions (Rs.Millions)	Assets Quality Ratio
2000 - 01	15462	32223.83	48.0
2001 - 02	15322	28170.15	54.4
2002 - 03	16716	29970.72	53.8
2003 - 04	16375	26728.35	61.3
2004 - 05	15867	31012.17	51.2
2005 - 06	13089	44851.48	29.2
2006 - 07	10616	55365.15	19.2
2007 - 08	2824	88022.17	3.2
2008 - 09	1367	66626.00	2.1
2009 - 10	1409	83967.00	1.7
2010 - 11	3197	103734.00	3.1
2011 - 12	5770.47	104740	5.5
2012 - 13	7246.10	102256	7.1

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2001-02 to 2012-13.

Figure 2, Assets Quality

INFERENCE: The results in Table 4 and figure 2 have shown that Assets Quality in APSFC has been satisfactory. SFC has been rated first up to 2006-07. Second rank rated from 2007-08 onwards for NPA performance with respect to advances performed well, which signifies that there is an effective control of Non Performing Assets over its Advances. It can be seen that the Assets Quality is fluctuate and satisfactory during the period.

Table 5. Management Efficiency Ratio

YEAR	Net Profit (Rs. Millions)	Employees (Rs. Millions)	Management Efficiency Ratio
2000-01	-11.67	730	-1.6
2001-02	-13.13	507	-2.2
2002-03	2.36	546	4.32
2003-04	10.1	534	1.9
2004-05	13.15	523	2.5
2005-06	24.50	519	4.8
2006-07	27.21	514	5.3
2007-08	09.51	502	17.8
2008-09	42.85	534	8.0
2009-10	67.68	517	13.1
2010-11	67.33	498	13.5
2011-12	68.33	466	14.7
2012-13	63.35	456	13.9

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2001-02 to 2012-13.

INFERENCE: The results in Table 5 and figure 3 have shown that Management Efficiency Ratio in APSFC has been satisfactory. SFC has been rated third rank and fourth rated from 2007-13 onwards for Net Profit per employee performance has been progressive trend. It implies that net profit per employee performance is improved year to year. It can be seen that the MER is fluctuate and satisfactory during the study period.

Table 6. Earnings Quality

YEAR	Net Profit After Tax (Rs. Millions)	Average Assets (Rs. Millions)	Earnings Quality
2000-01	-11.67	1257.83	-9.2
2001-02	-13.13	1188.15	-7.8
2002-03	2.36	1754.78	1.8

Table 6. Earnings Quality

YEAR	Net Profit After Tax (Rs. Millions)	Average Assets (Rs. Millions)	Earnings Quality
2003-04	10.1	1200.73	8.4
2004-05	13.15	1192.82	1.1
2005-06	24.58	1284.46	1.9
2006-07	27.21	1419.44	1.9
2007-08	89.51	1840.18	4.9
2008-09	42.85	1387.53	3.1
2009-10	67.68	1365.15	5.0
2010-11	67.33	1212.95	5.6
2011-12	68.33	2617.73	2.6
2012-13	63.35	2965.95	2.1

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2001-02 to 2012-13.

INFERENCE: The results in Table 6 and figure 4 have shown that Assets Quality Ratio in APSFC has been satisfactory. SFC has been rated second rank from the year 2002-03. For Net Profit after tax to average assets performance has fluctuated trend. It implies that net profit after tax to have been decreased year 2010 in between year 2013. It can be seen that the assets quality is not satisfactory during the study period.

Table 7, Liquidity Position

YEAR	Cash (Rs.Millions)	Recoveries (Rs.Millions)	Liquidity position
2000 - 01	57.23	295	19
2001 - 02	34.04	338	10
2002 - 03	73.12	408	18
2003 - 04	7133.89	45022	1.6
2004 - 05	5485.30	45139	12.2
2005 - 06	9011.55	48214	18.7
2006 - 07	10138	51595	19.6
2007 - 08	15817	62194	25.5
2008 - 09	7480	65808	11.4
2009 - 10	9661	78512	12.3
2010 - 11	15727	90238	17.4
2011 - 12	21550	96646	22.3
2012 - 13	24708	98999	25.0

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of APSFC from 2001-02 to 2012-13.

Figure 5, Liquidity Position

INFERENCE:

The results in Table 7 and figure 5 have shown that Liquidity Position in APSFC has been satisfactory. SFC has been rated fourth second and fourth rank rated from the year 2010-13 onwards for cash to recoveries performance has progressive trend. It implies that more liquidity has been maintained by SFC during the year 2009-13. It can be seen that the Liquidity Position is satisfactory during the study period.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES:

In this paper researcher has made five hypotheses based on camel model to know the operational and financial performance of APSFC. Used to single sample t-test for computing the appropriate t value to test the significance. The degrees of freedom for entering the t

Table: 8, t-test results for camel parameters of APSFC

S.No.	Efficiency parameters	Measurement Ratios	t-test	Significance	Hypothesis Result
1	Capital Adequacy	Capital Adequacy	5.68	.000	Rejected
2	Assets Quality	NPA to Advance	3.90	.002	Rejected
3	Management	Net profit for employees	4.04	.002	Rejected
4	Earning Quality	Return on Assets	1.28	.226	Accepted
5	Liquidity Position	Cash to Recoveries	8.82	.000	Rejected

Source: Computed

Table No. 8 presented the tested t- test results of given hypotheses; all parameters indicators are rejected except Earning Quality, which is accepted the hypothesis. The same supported by significant results; where capital adequacy and liquidity management have highly significant (.000) and Asset quality and management efficiency have (0.002) significance. Here researcher identified that Capital Adequacy, Assets Quality, Management Efficiency and Liquidity Position are good, but earning quality is to be improved.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS:

This study presents the major findings of the operating financial performance of APSFC over a period of thirteen years from 2000-2001 to 2012-2013. This part explains Financial Parameter Ratings and CAMEL Model Specifications the following observations were found, which are discussed here under.

- o It is observed that corporation has sufficient funds to meet its risk profile. It generates more funds and utilized purposefully.
- o APSFC is an effective control of Non Performing Assets over its Advances.
- o It observed that corporation net profit per employee performance is improved year to year.
- o Net profit after tax of the corporation has been decreased year 2010 in between year 2013. It is observed that the assets quality is not satisfactory during the study period.
- o It can be seen that more liquidity has been maintained by SFC during the year 2009-13. It is observed that Liquidity Position of the corporation is satisfactory.

To conclude, our findings from the operational and financial performance of APSFC are moderate during the study period. It is suggested that APSFC should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, debt and improving the productive efficiency of employees. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the corporation for better performance.

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